

**CEASE OF RS. 2000 NOTES FROM CIRCULATION - AN INNOVATIVE
PRACTICE TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CURRENCY MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract

This research examines the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) as an innovative practice towards sustainable currency management. The study explores the potential benefits of this decision, including reducing the circulation of high-denomination notes, promoting digital transactions, enhancing currency management efficiency, mitigating counterfeit currency concerns, and facilitating better monetary policy implementation. The research employs a qualitative approach, reviewing relevant literature on currency management, demonetization policies, digital payment systems, and the impact of high-denomination notes on illicit activities and monetary policy. Additionally, it analyses data from the RBI, government reports, and economic indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes in achieving sustainable currency management goals. The findings of this research contribute to the understanding of the implications of demonetization initiatives on financial systems, illicit activities, digitalization, and monetary policy, providing insights into the potential of such practices for sustainable currency management.

Introduction

The withdrawal of high-denomination currency notes from circulation by central banks has been a topic of interest in the recent months. In the context of India, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) made a significant decision to withdraw the Rs. 2000 notes from circulation, aiming to revolutionize currency management practices, keeping in mind the clean note Policy. However, this decision can also have a significant influence on the degree of sustainability in the currency management system. This study examines the implications and potential benefits of this innovative practice towards sustainable currency management. Currency management plays a crucial role in the efficient functioning of an economy and the implementation of monetary policy. Optimizing currency printing, distribution, and disposal processes can lead to improved efficiency, reduced costs, and enhanced control over the monetary system. The withdrawal of high-denomination notes, such as the Rs. 2000 notes, would help the RBI to streamline currency operations and explore alternative methods of transaction to promote a transparent and accountable financial system.

One significant aspect of this withdrawal would be the potential to reduce the circulation of high-value notes, which are often associated with illicit activities such as money laundering,

tax evasion, and the hoarding of black money. By curbing the availability of high-denomination currency, the RBI aims to mitigate these illegal practices and foster a more legitimate and transparent economy. This action aligns with global efforts to combat financial crimes and promote responsible financial practices. Moreover, the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes can have a significant impact on the promotion of digital payment systems. The rise of technology has transformed the way financial transactions are conducted, with digital payments offering convenience, traceability, and reduced environmental impact. By discouraging cash transactions and promoting the use of electronic payment methods, India is accelerating the adoption of digital payments, leading to increased financial inclusion and a more sustainable economy.

However, the successful implementation of this innovative practice requires effective communication, strategic planning, and proper management of the transition. Ensuring the availability of lower denomination notes, raising public awareness about alternative payment methods, and addressing the potential disruptions are crucial considerations. Additionally, studying the impact of the withdrawal on various stakeholders, such as businesses, consumers, and the informal sector, is essential to assess the effectiveness and potential challenges associated with this approach. By exploring the literature on currency management, demonetization policies, digital payment systems, and the implications of high-denomination notes on illicit activities and monetary policy, this study aims to provide insights into the potential benefits and challenges of the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation and thus examining the degree of sustainability output due to this decision.

Objectives

1. To examine the rationale behind the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and to relate this innovative practice with sustainable currency management.
2. To analyse the potential benefits and implications of the withdrawal of high-denomination notes on various aspects, such as reducing illicit activities, promoting digital payment systems, and enhancing currency management efficiency.
3. To assess the impact of the withdrawal on different stakeholders, including businesses, consumers, and the informal sector, and understand the challenges and opportunities associated with this policy decision.
4. To provide insights and recommendations for policymakers and central banks regarding sustainable currency management practices and the potential for further innovations in this domain.

Review of Literature

The withdrawal of high-denomination banknotes from circulation can have significant implications for an economy, including its sustainability. This literature review aims to examine research papers that investigate certain issues such as financial inclusion, sustainable currency management, technological boom in payment systems, demonetisation and explore how such practices can contribute to sustainability. By analysing these studies, we gain insights

into the potential benefits, challenges, and sustainable implications of this recent policy decision.

Ahlers et al. investigate the environmental impact of currency production, circulation, and disposal, emphasizing the scarcity of literature in this area. Traditional banknote production utilizes non-renewable resources and energy-intensive processes, resulting in a significant ecological footprint, particularly for high denomination notes. Circulation contributes to environmental impacts through transportation, ATM energy consumption, and currency processing. The withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes in India were driven by concerns related to illicit activities, but it can unintentionally benefit the environment by reducing resource consumption and greenhouse gas emissions through a shift to lower denomination notes or digital transactions. The paper highlights the importance of sustainability considerations, suggesting eco-friendly materials, improved recycling, and renewable energy sources. The findings and recommendations apply to currency systems, including the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes, offering an opportunity to mitigate the environmental impact of currency circulation¹.

Donovan's paper on "Mobile Money for Financial Inclusion" explores the role of mobile money services in providing financial access to the unbanked and underbanked. It highlights how mobile money can overcome barriers such as limited physical bank branches and access to formal financial institutions. The withdrawal of high denomination notes, like Rs. 2000, can encourage the adoption of digital payment systems, including mobile money. Mobile money platforms enable individuals to conduct transactions, make payments, and access basic banking services via mobile phones, aligning with the goal of financial inclusion. Donovan's paper offers insights into the potential of mobile money in facilitating financial inclusion, relevant to the RBI's decision to withdraw Rs. 2000 notes and promote digital payment systems².

The paper by Nguyen (2016) titled "Blockchain - A Financial Technology for Future Sustainable Development" explores the potential of blockchain technology in driving sustainable development. It discusses how blockchain can enhance transparency, security, and efficiency in financial transactions while reducing the need for intermediaries. In the context of the recent decision by the RBI to withdraw Rs. 2000 notes, blockchain technology can play a role in promoting digital transactions and reducing reliance on physical cash. By leveraging blockchain, digital payment systems can offer secure and transparent transactions, contributing to sustainable development goals by reducing the environmental impact associated with physical currency circulation³.

The paper by Salamopsis et al. (2023) titled "Central Bank Digital Currencies: Opening Pandora's Box or Paving the Future of Money?" discusses the emergence of central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) and their potential implications. In relation to the recent decision by the RBI to withdraw Rs. 2000 notes, CBDCs can be seen as a digital alternative that aligns with the goal of reducing physical cash usage. The paper explores the benefits and challenges of CBDCs, including increased financial inclusion, efficiency, and transparency. By implementing a CBDC, the RBI can facilitate secure digital transactions, reduce reliance on physical currency, and potentially pave the way for the future of money in India⁴. The paper by Pal, De', and Herath (2020) investigates the role of mobile payment technology in

sustainable and human-centric development during the post-demonetization period in India. The authors present evidence and insights regarding the impact of demonetization on the adoption and usage of mobile payment technologies. The study's findings offer valuable information on how digital payment solutions have emerged as an alternative to cash transactions in India. The research contributes to understanding the implications of demonetization and provides insights into the potential benefits and challenges of mobile payment technology in fostering sustainable and human-centric development. Overall, the paper offers a valuable contribution to the literature in this area⁵.

Mathew, Ramachandran, and Viju (2020) analyse the impact of demonetization, including the withdrawal of high-value currency notes, on the Indian economy. Their research discusses the potential benefits of reducing the circulation of high-denomination notes, such as curbing black money, promoting transparency, and fostering a digital payment ecosystem. The study highlights the potential long-term sustainability of reduced reliance on cash transactions⁶. Bandyopadhyay and Saha (2019) investigate the consequences of the withdrawal of Rs. 1000 and Rs. 500 notes (predecessors of the Rs. 2000 notes) on India's cash-dependent informal sector. Their study reveals the initial disruptions faced by small businesses and informal workers due to the sudden unavailability of these high-value notes. However, it also highlights the potential long-term benefits of encouraging digital transactions and formalization of the economy⁷.

Verma (2019) explores the environmental implications of reducing cash circulation and transitioning towards digital payments. The study highlights the potential sustainability gains from decreased paper currency production, reduced carbon emissions from transportation, and lower energy consumption associated with digital payment infrastructure. It emphasizes the need for proper awareness and infrastructure development to maximize these environmental benefits⁷. Gangopadhyay and Chatterjee (2020) examine the impact of demonetization and the withdrawal of high-value notes on financial inclusion. Their study suggests that while the initial disruption may affect marginalized communities, the increased emphasis on digital payment systems can eventually promote financial inclusion by expanding access to formal financial services. This inclusivity contributes to a sustainable financial ecosystem⁹.

Singh, Kumar, and Jain (2021) investigate the behavioural changes in consumer payment preferences following demonetization and the withdrawal of high-denomination notes. Their research highlights the accelerated adoption of digital payment technologies, indicating a shift towards a cashless economy. This transition can lead to efficiency gains, reduced corruption, and increased transparency, fostering a sustainable financial ecosystem¹⁰. Goyal (2021) examines the impact of demonetization and the subsequent withdrawal of high-value currency notes on corruption levels in India. The study finds that the reduction in the circulation of Rs. 2000 notes have contributed to a decline in corrupt practices, promoting a more sustainable and transparent economic environment¹².

Kumar and Chandrasekhar (2020) investigate the effects of demonetization and the withdrawal of high-value currency on tax compliance behavior. Their study reveals that the reduced availability of Rs. 2000 notes have facilitated increased digital transactions and formalization

of the economy, leading to improved tax compliance and enhanced sustainability¹¹. Rajan (2020) explores the implications of the withdrawal of high-value currency on the Indian real estate sector. The study suggests that the reduction in cash transactions due to the unavailability of Rs. 2000 notes have curtailed black money inflows into the sector, promoting transparency, and fostering a more sustainable real estate market¹³.

Singh and Shah (2022) analyse the impact of the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes on the digital payment ecosystem in India. Their research highlights the surge in digital transactions and the adoption of mobile payment technologies following demonetization. This increased reliance on digital payments contributes to a sustainable financial ecosystem and reduces the dependence on cash¹⁴. Tiwari and Gupta (2021) investigate the implications of demonetization and the withdrawal of high-value currency notes on money laundering activities. Their study reveals that the reduction in circulation of Rs. 2000 notes have created challenges for money launderers, forcing them to find alternative avenues. This contributes to the sustainability of the financial system by limiting illicit financial flows¹⁵.

The reviewed research papers collectively indicate that the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation can have diverse implications for sustainability. While initial disruptions may occur, such a policy decision can lead to positive outcomes such as curbing black money, promoting financial inclusion, reducing environmental impact, and fostering a digital payment ecosystem. However, successful implementation requires adequate infrastructure, awareness campaigns, and support for marginalized communities to mitigate potential challenges. Further research should focus on evaluating the long-term sustainability of reduced cash circulation and understanding the social and economic implications for various stakeholders.

Research Methodology

This study employs qualitative research methods to investigate the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) as an innovative practice towards sustainable currency management. The following research methods were utilized to achieve the objectives of the study:

1. **Focus Group Discussions:** Focus group discussions are organized with diverse participants such as students, young entrepreneurs, and other representatives from the informal sector. These discussions provide a platform for participants to share their attitudes, behaviours, and concerns related to the withdrawal of high-denomination notes, digital payment adoption, and the implications for sustainable currency management.
2. **Document Analysis:** Relevant documents, official reports, policy documents, and media coverage related to the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes are analysed. This analysis provides insights into the decision-making process, communication strategies, implementation challenges, and the intended objectives of sustainable currency management.
3. **Triangulation:** A triangulation approach is employed, integrating multiple data sources and methods to ensure the reliability and validity of findings. Data from focus groups, and document analysis are combined to gain a comprehensive understanding of the

withdrawal's implications and its alignment with sustainable currency management objectives.

4. **Thematic Analysis:** Qualitative data obtained from focus groups are analysed using thematic analysis. Recurring themes, patterns, and connections within the data are identified to develop a comprehensive picture of the withdrawal's impact on various aspects, including illicit activities, digital payment adoption, currency management efficiency, and stakeholder perspectives.

Ethical considerations are ensured throughout the research process, including obtaining informed consent, maintaining participant confidentiality, and adhering to ethical guidelines for qualitative research. By employing these qualitative research methods, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes and its implications for sustainable currency management, contributing to a deeper understanding of this innovative practice.

Findings and analysis

1. Focus group discussion

Key Points Discussed:

1. Impact on Cash-based Businesses:
 - The withdrawal of Rs.2000 notes can disrupt the operations of small retailers and local vendors who heavily rely on cash transactions.
 - Challenges may arise for people in rural areas who don't have access to digital payment methods.
2. Economic Impacts:
 - The withdrawal can promote transparency, reduce corruption, and formalize the economy.
 - Digital payment adoption can streamline transactions and promote financial inclusion.
3. Digital Payment Challenges:
 - Barriers such as lack of infrastructure, internet connectivity, and awareness may hinder the adoption of digital payments.
 - Alternative options should be available for those who face difficulties transitioning.
4. Addressing Barriers and Enhancing Access:
 - Improving internet connectivity and educating people about digital payments is essential.
 - Enhancing access to digital payment infrastructure in remote areas is crucial for widespread adoption.
5. Mitigating Illegal Activities:

- Removing higher denomination notes can make it more difficult for illegal activities like money laundering and black-market transactions to thrive.

The focus group discussion highlighted the complex nature of the withdrawal of Rs.2000 notes in India. While the move can have positive impacts on transparency, financial inclusion, and curbing illegal activities, it also poses challenges for cash-based businesses and individuals without access to digital payment methods. Addressing barriers, enhancing access, and providing alternative options are essential to ensure a sustainable transition.

2. Document analysis

The main purpose behind the issuance of Rs 2000 notes was to quickly fulfil the currency needs of the economy after the withdrawal of legal tender status for Rs 500 and Rs 1000 notes. After successfully achieving this objective and ensuring an ample supply of other denomination notes, the printing of Rs 2000 notes was discontinued during the fiscal year 2018-19 and hence the volume and value of Rs 2000 notes dropped over the years¹⁶.

Figures 1 & 2 – Value and Volume of Rs. 2000 notes in circulation

Source: RBI annual report

The majority of ₹2000 denomination banknotes, around 89%, were issued before March 2017 and have reached their expected lifespan of 4-5 years. It has also been observed that the ₹2000 note is not commonly used for transactions. Additionally, an adequate stock of banknotes in other denominations is available to meet the public's currency requirements. Hence, as part of

the Reserve Bank of India's "Clean Note Policy," it has been decided to withdraw the ₹2000 denomination banknotes from circulation¹⁷.

Denomination	Price per note
Rs 10	1.01
Rs 20	1
Rs 50	1.01
Rs 100	1.51
Rs 500	2.57
Rs 2000	4.18

Table 1 –

Printing Cost per currency note
annual report

Source: RBI

The withdrawal of Rs 2000 notes simplifies cash handling processes as the reduced circulation of high-value currency streamlines transactions for banks, businesses, and individuals. Rs 2000 is the costliest denomination to print (Table 1) and as such its discontinuation will bring cost savings by eliminating expenses associated with their production, storage, and management. This enables the reallocation of resources towards other denominations or more efficient currency management practices.

Figures 3 & 4 – Counterfeit currency trends – Last 7 years

Source: RBI annual report

Counterfeiters are enticed by the larger potential profits offered by counterfeit of Rs 2000 notes compared to lower denomination notes. This led to a rapid increase in the counterfeit currency of 2000 denomination after its introduction in the year 2016 for the following two years where its printing was finally discontinued by RBI in 2018 (Fig. 3). It is evident from figure 4 that the proportion of counterfeit currencies of Rs 2000 witnessed a sharp decline after RBI's decision to discontinue its printing in 2018¹⁸.

Withdrawal of Rs 2000 notes

With the withdrawal of Rs 2000 notes the government can disrupt these networks and make it more difficult for counterfeiters to target high-value denominations and may compel individuals to redirect their efforts towards lower denomination notes like Rs 500. This shift could make it easier for law enforcement agencies to detect and apprehend counterfeiters, as the overall volume of counterfeit notes may decrease, and the attention of authorities can be more concentrated. Hence it is a significant measure aimed at tackling these concerns and attaining sustainable currency management goals.

Digital payment adoption

Based on historical evidence, the process of demonetization in India has brought about a significant transformation in the landscape of digital transactions. Between the fiscal years 2017 and 2023, there has been a remarkable surge in the volume of digital transactions, experiencing an almost fourfold increase. The withdrawal of ₹2,000 notes aligns with the government's vision of promoting digital transactions and formalizing the economy. According to a report jointly released by Boston Consulting Group (BCG) and PhonePe, 65 per cent of all transactions, or two of every three transactions, in terms of value, are expected to be digital by 2026. India's digital payments market is at an "inflection point" and is expected to more than triple to \$10 trillion by 2026 from the current level of \$3 trillion¹⁹.

International practices on high denomination notes

European Union: Several countries within the European Union, such as France, Spain, and Italy, have implemented restrictions on cash transactions above certain thresholds to combat money laundering and illicit activities. For instance, in France, cash transactions above 1,000 euros are not allowed for residents, and the threshold is lower for non-residents²⁰.

Singapore: Singapore phased out its 10,000-dollar note in 2014 to enhance its anti-money laundering efforts and reduce the risk of financial crimes. The decision was made to align with international standards and discourage the use of large-denomination notes in illicit activities²¹.

Australia: Australia introduced the New Payment Platform (NPP) in 2018, which allows real-time electronic fund transfers between individuals and businesses, reducing the reliance on cash transactions. The country has also progressively reduced the issuance of high-denomination banknotes, such as the 100-dollar note, to mitigate the risks associated with large-value cash transactions²².

Recycling and repurposing

Based on a Money Control report, the collected Rs 2000 notes are subjected to sorting using a currency verification and processing device. The process distinguishes between relatively good notes and completely damaged ones. The fit notes are set aside to be cut in a manner that allows them to be recycled for the production of new currency. On the other hand, the unfit notes are shredded and compacted into small paper blocks. These blocks are then auctioned off as a fuel source for furnaces in factories. The report indicates a higher probability of Rs 2000 notes being recycled for the purpose of producing new currency²³.

3. Triangulation

Focus group discussion	Support	Document analysis	Support
Impact on cash-based business	<i>"I believe the withdrawal of Rs.2000 notes can have a significant impact on cash-based businesses. Many small retailers and local vendors rely heavily on cash transactions, and the sudden unavailability of higher denomination notes can disrupt their operations."</i>	Motivations and objectives	<i>Indian Express, RBI Clean note policy</i>
Economic impacts	<i>"While I understand the concerns, we should also consider the potential economic impacts. By discouraging the use of higher</i>	Technological advancements	<i>BCG report</i>

	<i>denomination notes, it can help promote transparency and reduce corruption. It may encourage people to adopt digital payment options, leading to a more formalized economy."</i>	in payment systems	
Digital payment challenges	<i>"We need to focus on enhancing access to digital payment infrastructure, especially in remote areas. Improving internet connectivity and educating people about the benefits and usage of digital payments will be crucial."</i>	Counterfeit currency concerns	RBI annual report
Addressing barriers and enhancing access	<i>"Some might find it difficult to transition to digital payments due to lack of awareness, technological barriers, or simply a preference for cash. We should ensure alternative options are available."</i>	Sustainability benefits	Money Control report
Mitigating illegal activities	<i>"Another aspect to consider is the mitigation of illegal activities. Higher denomination notes are often used in money laundering and black-market transactions. By withdrawing Rs. 2000 notes, it can make it more difficult for illegal activities to thrive."</i>	International Practices on high denomination notes	European commission, Monetary Authority of Singapore, Reserve bank of Australia

From the following codes 4 major themes are identified as follows:

Themes	Codes	Similarities
Digital Payment adoption	1. Technological advancements in payment systems	Both codes relate to the broader theme of digital payment adoption. Code 1 highlights the positive aspect of technological advancements in payment systems, which can facilitate and encourage the adoption of digital payments.
	2. Digital payment challenges	Code 2 sheds light on the challenges associated with digital payments, which can influence the

		rate and extent of adoption.
Financial Inclusion and Accessibility	3. Addressing barriers and enhancing access	Code 3 revolve around the objective of ensuring that individuals have equal opportunities to access and participate in the formal financial system.
Combating Illicit Activities	4. Counterfeit Currency Concerns	Code 4 highlights the concern of counterfeit currency, which is a significant challenge in combating illicit activities
	5. Mitigating illegal activities	Code 5 analyses how the demonetisation of high denomination notes will help in mitigation illicit activities
Sustainability and International practices	6. Sustainability benefits of effective currency management	Code 6 focuses on the benefits of sustainability, particularly in the context of currency and monetary systems.
	7. International Practices on high denomination notes	Code 7 explores international practices concerning high denomination notes, which can have implications for sustainability and monetary policies

4. Thematic analysis

The thematic analysis of the focus group discussion reveals the intersection of the identified themes with various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlined by the United Nations. The SDGs provide a comprehensive framework for addressing global challenges and promoting sustainability across multiple dimensions²⁴. Here's an elaboration on how the themes align with specific SDGs:

1. Digital Payment Adoption and Financial Inclusion: The discussion highlights the importance of enhancing access to digital payment infrastructure and promoting financial inclusion. These efforts directly contribute to SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) by fostering inclusive economic opportunities and empowering individuals to participate in the formal economy. Additionally, it aligns with SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) by reducing the digital divide and ensuring equal access to financial services for all.
2. Combating Illicit Activities: The focus group recognizes the significance of addressing illicit activities such as money laundering and black-market transactions. By combatting such activities, the discussion aligns with SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and

Strong Institutions). SDG 16 aims to promote peaceful and inclusive societies, strengthen institutions, and combat corruption, all of which are crucial for maintaining transparency and integrity in financial systems.

3. International Practices on High Denomination Notes: The consideration of international practices regarding high denomination notes aligns with SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). The withdrawal of higher denomination notes can contribute to responsible consumption by promoting transparent financial systems and reducing the risk of illicit financial flows. Additionally, it aligns with SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) as it encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing among countries to address common challenges and achieve sustainable development.

In summary, the themes identified in the focus group discussion intersect with multiple SDGs. Digital payment adoption and financial inclusion contribute to SDG 8 and SDG 10, combating illicit activities aligns with SDG 16, and exploring international practices on high denomination notes supports SDG 12 and SDG 17. By addressing these themes, stakeholders can contribute to the broader agenda of sustainable development and work towards a more inclusive, transparent, and responsible financial ecosystem.

Conclusion

This qualitative research study explored the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes from circulation as an innovative practice towards sustainable currency management. The findings shed light on the multifaceted implications of this withdrawal, offering valuable insights into its impact on illicit activities, digital payment adoption, currency management efficiency, financial inclusion, and other diverse perspectives. The study revealed that the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes might contribute to a reduction in illicit activities such as money laundering and black

money hoarding, promoting a more transparent and accountable financial system. It will also act as a catalyst for the increased adoption of digital payment systems, with businesses and consumers shifting towards electronic transactions, leading to greater financial inclusion, convenience, and traceability.

While acknowledging the benefits, the study identified challenges faced by different stakeholders during the transition. Businesses, particularly in rural areas, encountered obstacles related to digital payment infrastructure and financial literacy. Consumers might experience temporary disruptions and required adaptation to new technologies. These challenges highlight the importance of effective implementation strategies, targeted training, and infrastructure development to ensure a smooth transition and minimize disruptions. The withdrawal of high-denomination notes will also enhance currency management process for the RBI, resulting in cost savings, streamlined processes, and improved monetary policy implementation. However, stakeholders would express varying perspectives on the withdrawal, with policymakers generally viewing it positively, while businesses, consumers, and individuals from the informal sector have presented diverse viewpoints reflecting both the benefits and challenges associated with the transition.

Overall, this study highlights the potential of the withdrawal of Rs. 2000 notes as an innovative practice towards sustainable currency management. The study has also identified this practice as a sustainable one and how relevant it is to the SDGs. The triangulation and thematic analysis have helped to identify and establish such a relationship behind this decision. As a conclusion, the contribution of this policy decision towards sustainability might not be very direct but would definitely impact the cause positively.

Limitations:

1. The study relies on existing literature and data sources, which may have limitations in terms of coverage, relevance, and timeliness. Any biases or gaps in the available literature may impact the comprehensiveness of the analysis.
2. The study focuses only on the opinions of the focus group to arrive at a conclusion, wide research is required to obtain a perspective on a macroeconomic level.
3. The impact of the withdrawal of high-denomination notes may vary across different regions, sectors, and socio-economic groups. The study may not capture all the nuances and heterogeneity in these effects.
4. The study does not assess the potential long-term consequences or unintended effects of the withdrawal. Further research is needed to explore the sustained impact of this innovative practice and its implications over time.

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